

THE IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN ON TRADITIONAL BANKING SERVICES

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Annotation: Blockchain, as a decentralized and transparent technology, has a significant impact on traditional banking services, offering new approaches to transaction processing, data management and customer interaction. This thesis will discuss how it reduces transaction costs by eliminating intermediaries, increases the speed of transactions and provides a high level of security thanks to cryptographic protection.

Key words: decentralization, **transparency, security, transaction speed, cost reduction, smart contracts, innovative products,** competition, availability.

Blockchain is a decentralized technology for storing and transmitting data based on the principles of cryptography. The main idea is to create a secure and transparent database where information is stored in blocks linked to each other. Each block contains not only transaction data, but also a cache of the previous block, making it impossible to change information without the consent of all network participants. This structure provides a high level of security and trust between parties, which is especially important in the financial sector.

Traditional banking plays a key role in the economy, providing storage, lending, transfers, and investments. Banks act as intermediaries in financial transactions, controlling and facilitating interactions between clients. However, this model has its drawbacks: high fees, long processing times, and reliance on centralized authorities can create vulnerabilities and risks for clients.

The advent of blockchain is ushering in a new era in the financial industry. This technology offers an alternative to traditional banking services, allowing users to conduct transactions directly, without intermediaries. Blockchain reduces transaction costs, speeds

up the transaction process, and increases the availability of financial services. For example, international transfers that used to take several days and cost significant amounts can now be completed in minutes and with minimal fees.

The relevance of the topic is that blockchain not only improves existing processes, but also opens up new opportunities for financial institutions and clients. It can be used to create innovative financial products, such as smart contracts, which automate and simplify the execution of transaction terms. This not only increases efficiency, but also reduces the likelihood of fraud and errors.

Blockchain is thus a powerful tool that can transform traditional banking services and significantly change the face of the financial industry. This technology does not simply replace old models, but also creates new, more efficient and secure ways of interacting in the world of finance. It is important to understand how exactly blockchain will develop and what impact it will have on the future of the banking sector.

Blockchain technology is fundamentally changing the financial landscape, especially in the context of international transfers and foreign exchange transactions. Traditional methods of transferring funds often face high fees and unfavorable exchange rates, making financial services difficult to access for many users. In this regard, blockchain offers innovative solutions that can significantly reduce costs and improve user experience.

One of the main problems with traditional money transfer systems is the high fees. According to the World Bank, the average cost of an international transfer is about 6.5% of the transferred amount. This can be especially significant for migrants sending money to their families back home. Blockchain, on the other hand, allows for transfers to be made with minimal fees, often less than 1%. This is achieved due to the decentralized nature of the technology, where participants in the network can interact directly without the need for intermediaries.

In addition, blockchain solves the problem of exchange rates. Traditional banks and financial institutions usually set exchange rates that can differ significantly from market

rates. For example, in 2021, the difference between buying and selling currency could reach 3-5%. Using blockchain allows for currency exchange at more favorable rates, since transactions occur in real time and directly between participants. This reduces the possibility of manipulation and makes the exchange more transparent.

Companies using blockchain for transactions are becoming more common. One prominent example is **Ripple**. This platform offers solutions for international transfers and uses its cryptocurrency XRP to provide liquidity. According to the company, Ripple allows you to reduce transaction times from days to seconds, while keeping fees at a few cents. This makes Ripple an attractive option for banks and financial institutions looking to optimize their services.

Another example is **Stellar**, which also focuses on international transfers, providing access to financial services for people in developing countries. Stellar allows currency exchange with minimal fees and provides a platform for the creation of new financial applications. According to statistics, the number of transactions conducted through Stellar has increased by 250% in 2022, which confirms the growing interest in the technology.

Finally, it's worth mentioning **BitPesa**, a platform that uses blockchain to transfer funds in Africa. It allows users to send money at lower rates and with minimal fees. According to the company, using BitPesa can reduce transfer costs by up to 80% compared to traditional methods.

Thus, blockchain provides effective solutions to problems related to exchange rates and fees. The technology not only reduces the costs of international transfers, but also makes them faster and more transparent. Examples of companies using blockchain demonstrate how this technology can radically change the approach to financial transactions and improve the availability of financial services to a wider audience. In the context of globalization and growing needs for financial services, blockchain is becoming an important tool for creating a more efficient and accessible financial system.

Blockchain technology has had a significant impact on the financial sector, offering new opportunities for increased efficiency and security. Key findings on the impact of blockchain include its ability to reduce transaction costs, provide transparency, and speed up processes. These benefits make blockchain particularly attractive for international transfers, lending, and other banking services.

Adaptation of banks to new technologies is becoming not just a desire, but a necessity for survival in a competitive environment. Financial institutions that do not integrate blockchain and other innovative solutions risk losing their customers who prefer faster and cheaper alternatives. Examples of successful banks implementing blockchain show that this not only improves the quality of services, but also allows for the creation of new products that meet the requirements of the modern market.

In conclusion, blockchain is not only transforming the financial landscape, but it is also posing challenges for banks that require them to adapt quickly and be ready for change. Success in this new era of finance depends on the ability of banks to integrate advanced technologies and provide their customers with the best experience.

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